

NORMAL TAQSIMLANGAN TANLANMAGA TORTILGAN QAVARIQ QOPLAMA FUNKSIONALLARI XOSSALARI XAQIDA.

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Faraz qilaylik P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n tekislikda bog'liqsiz bir xil normal taqsimlangan nuqtalar va C_n ularga tortilgan qavariq qoplama bo'lsin, u holda mos ravishda v_n , s_n va l_n lar yordamida C_n ning uchlarning soni, yuzasi va perimetrini belgilaymiz.

Ushbu maqolada [1-3] maqolalardagi tadqiqotlar davom ettirilib, normal taqsimlangan tanlanmaga tortilgan qavariq qoplama funkcionallarining ba'zi xossalari keltirilgan.

Qavariq qoplamalarni tadqiq qilish tarixida birinchi marotaba eng katta siljish yasalgan maqola P.Groeneboom [1] ga tegishli bo'lib, unda chegaralangan soxadagi binomial taqsimlangan nuqtaviy jarayonni Puasson nuqtaviy jarayoni bilan approksimatsiyalashtirilib qavariq qoplama uchlarning soni uchun limit teoremlar isbotladi. Keyinchalik I. Huter [2] P.Groeneboom usulini normal taqsimlangan tanlanmaga tortilgan qavariq qoplama funkcionallarining limit teoremlarini isbotlashga qo'lladi va quyidagi natijalarni oldi

$$\frac{v_n - 2\sqrt{2\pi \ln n}}{2\sqrt{2\pi \ln n}(1 + \pi c)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0,1), \quad \frac{l_n - 2\pi\sqrt{2 \ln n}}{\sqrt{4\pi^2 \ln n}} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0,1) \quad \text{BA}$$

$$\frac{s_n - 2\pi \ln n}{\sqrt{2\pi^2 \ln^2 n}} \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0,1).$$

Ta'rif. Ixtiyoriy $a \in R$ uchun P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n nuqtalar ichida $Y_k - aX_k$ ifodaga minimal qiymat beruvchi $P_k = (X_k, Y_k)$ nuqta a ga mos keluvchi qavariq qoplamaning uchlari jarayoni deyiladi va $W_n(a) = P_k$ deb belgilanadi.

Agar

$$r_0(n) = \sqrt{2 \ln n}, \quad r_1(n) = r_0(n) - \frac{\varepsilon_n}{2}, \quad r_2(n) = r_0(n) + \frac{\varepsilon_n}{2}$$

va

$$A_n^* = \left\{ (x, y) : r_2(n) \leq \sqrt{x^2 + (y - r_2(n))^2} \leq r_2(n) \right\}$$

Bo'lsa, u holda quyidagi teorema o'rinli bo'ladi

Teoremlar. $\varepsilon_n \rightarrow 0, \varepsilon_n r_0(n) \rightarrow \infty, n \rightarrow \infty$ shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi shuningdek ε_n mavjudki, agar $n \rightarrow \infty$ bo'lsa $P(W_n(a) \in A_n^*, \forall a \in R) \rightarrow 1$ o'rinli bo'ladi.

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